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IMPROVING THE WRITING SKILLS OF KINDERGARTEN LEARNERS USING THE PROJECT ECCW (EVERY CHILD CAN WRITE) OF PROGRESO ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

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Abstract

The main purpose of this study is to improve the writing ability of kindergarten learners using Project ECCW (Every Child Can Write). The study used the quasi-experimental method of research, Teacher-made worksheet pre and post test to determine the significant differences in the level of writing skills of kindergarten learners of Progreso Elementary School. The study used Project ECCW or Every Child Can Write. The researcher employed purposefully selected 25 Kindergarten Pupils as the responders. T-test and Mean percentage were the statistical instruments employed. Given the difference of 15.76%, the analysis revealed that after implementing Project ECCW, the MPS significantly rose from 37.28% to 53.04%. Because the calculated t-value 6.80 is more than the t-critical value 2.063 (>0.05), indicating a significant difference, the null hypothesis is rejected. This study showed a positive outcome and suggested that Project ECCW is an effective intervention for raising learners' writing ability. The researcher recommended that these intervention materials can be used by other Kindergarten teachers. All the necessary data gathered were treated accordingly. The study likewise implies that using Project ECCW can enhance the writing ability of kindergarten learners.

I. Context and Rationale

Handwriting is one of the fine motor skills that are important to develop in early childhood education. This action research is about the problem encountered by the researcher to her Kindergarten- Lavender wherein most of the pupil's struggle in writing their names and correct letter formation. As a kindergarten teacher for the past seven years, I have noticed a pattern among my pupils. Even after receiving formal instruction, I've found out that many kids are still struggling with handwriting and proper letter formation. I'm concerned about this since it affects students' ability to write. In my observation, many pupils displayed difficulties with fine motor activities like cutting and coloring. These kids frequently lack engagement and self-assurance when participating in any writing assignment.

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In the context of this research, in my current kindergarten class, I have identified several students who struggle significantly with handwriting. I've noticed that few of my students have serious handwriting issues. There are several reasons why these pupils are still having difficulties while the rest of the class is making regular developments. Some of the pupils didn't go to Day Care or any other type of education before kindergarten. Due to a lack of practice at home and school, the hand muscles that support fine motor abilities may be weak. Another factor is their cognitive aspect. These are the reasons why I want to make changes in my kindergarten class is to enhance my instruction as a kindergarten teacher, I used intervention in assessing handwriting difficulties and practicing fine motor skills through teaching. This is to ensure that pupils are learning the proper way to write letters and numbers using the concepts of different lines & strokes through practice and teacher-made activity sheets. These considerations prompted us to provide opportunities to address individual needs in writing of Kindergarten-Lavender through the implementation of Project ECCW .

II. Action Research Questions

This study aims to determine the perceive impact of addressing Writing skills among kindergarten pupils in using Project ECCW (Every Child Can Write). Specifically, this study answers the following questions:

1. What is the level of writing skills of Kindergarten Pupils before and after implementation of Project ECCW in Progreso Elementary School?
2. Is there a significant difference in the level of writing skills of Kindergarten Pupils before and after the implementation of Project ECCW in Progreso Elementary School?
3. What are the implications of the findings of this Action Research for improving the writing skills of Kindergarten Pupils of Progreso Elementary School?

Action Research Methods

A. Participants and/or other Sources of Data and Information

The action research made use of quasi-experimental method employing the one group pretest-posttest design. Kindergarten learners first took the 15-item pre-test to determine their handwriting ability. Afterwards, the Project ECCW (Every Child Can Write) was employed, which lasted for several sessions. A post-test was then administered after the use of Project ECCW intervention. The study was conducted in Progreso Elementary school. The researchers chose this locale since this is also where the researcher is practicing her profession. There was no sampling procedure to be used among 25 kindergarten pupils as there was a complete enumeration of the said respondents.

B. Data Gathering Methods

The researcher selected the methods and research methodology for the study. The principal's approval and recommendation were requested. Following the approval of the initial permission, the researcher conducted the orientation and obtained further permits for the parents or legal guardians of the targeted respondents. The study's goals, administration plan, and research method were then covered at an orientation for parents and guardians. Teachers made worksheets were the research instruments employed. The researcher gave the kindergarten learners a pre-test to gauge their writing level based on their ability. The researcher personally conducted the pre-test during the remedial class to guarantee that the results were valid because there were criteria followed in marking and scoring the writing skills of the learners. To determine if the students' writing ability has improved after the Project ECCW (Every Child Can Write) integration, a posttest was given to the kindergarten learners. This was done on the Second Quarter of the School Year. Consequently, posttest was easily

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administered. Data were gathered to enable an adequate statistical analysis. Calculations, data processing, and analysis and data interpretation, as well as the creation of improvement suggestions were done.

C. Data Analysis

The data collected were based on the pre assessment and post assessment results. The researcher used the writing skills tests as the pre and post sources of data. The primary instrument used was the Project ECCW as the main intervention. The intervention was conducted for First and Second Grading in School Year 2023-2024. In finding the significant difference, the researcher used the paired t-test statistical tool. This tool compares two means that are from the same individual, object, or related units. The two means can represent things.

The formula for t-test is shown as:

Where:

t= t value

x = mean of difference of paired value

U = population mean

S = standard deviation

n = number of samples

III. Discussion of Results and Reflection

Writing Skills Level and the Mean Percentage Score of Twenty-five (25) Kindergarten-Lavender learners in Progreso Elementary School and After the implementation of Project ECCW

	Weighted Mean	MPS	N	SD
PRETEST	74.56	37.28	25	8.63
POSTTEST	106.08	53.04	25	10.3

Table 1 shows the comparison between the level of performance and the mean percentage score of twenty-five Kindergarten pupils in the Pre-Test and post-test. Based on the results, it was found that the Weighted Mean is equal to 74.56 and 106.08 which brings to the MPS of 37.28 and 53.04 percent and resulted in a Standard Deviation which is equal to 8.63 and 10.3 The outcome revealed that the Mean, MPS, and SD of the pretest and posttest varied by 31.52, 15.76, and 1.67, respectively.

The findings implied that Project ECCW is a successful intervention for teaching writing. This is an indication that the utilization of the project helped the respondents improve their level of writing skills. The intervention conducted considerably benefited the teaching-learning process.

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<i>Variables Compared</i>	<i>Means</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Computed t value</i>	<i>Critical t value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Impression 0.05</i>
PRETEST	74.56	24	6.8	2.063	Reject H ₀	Significant
POSTTEST	106.08					

Table 2 revealed the significant difference in the level of writing skills of kindergarten learners of Progreso Elementary School before and after the implementation of Project ECCW wherein the computed t- t-value was 6.8 and 2.063 t-critical value, degree of freedom (df) at the 0.05 level of significance. The computed t-value is greater than the t-tabular value, therefore, reject the null hypothesis (H₀). This indicates how the project's implementation resulted in a notable improvement in the level of writing ability.

IV. IMPLICATIONS

The study implied that given the respondents are from Key Stage 1, particularly in kindergarten, they truly require direction, and the support and assistance of parents and guardians at home has a big impact on the kids' education. The findings go on to show, that Project ECCW is a tool that potentially improved the level of writing ability because they can easily understand the formation of letters through different lines and strokes. Since Project ECCW materials are printed, learners can practice and bring them at home. As a result, the project was a success because it assisted Kindergarten learners, who are just learning how to write letters at this age.

Teaching Kindergarten writing ability through the implementation of Project ECCW seems to be impressive considering the results the pupils achieved in terms of their writing performance. Given that pupils are just beginning to develop their writing skills in this difficult world, facing the new normal of learning new things, it can help teachers greatly in improving their knowledge of how to properly teach the learners and develop their skills. Teachers must apply strategies and approaches that will suit the interests of a young learner. They should adopt the trend of teaching them to arouse the interest of learners, especially in writing letters that require motivation. Also, successful literacy intervention programs help students succeed. Helping struggling learners build positive writing habits truly helped them to be ready in Grade One.

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Curriculum Vitae

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